

e

Project Proposition

**Sustainable software
2023 (SS 2023)**

e

General

Please refer to the Call for Proposals "Call for Sustainable software (SS 2023)" for the Terms and Conditions of this granting scheme. The call text is available at <https://www.esciencecenter.nl/calls-for-proposals>.

Proposals must be submitted using the ISAAC submission system: <https://www.isaac.nwo.nl/> (see below for details).

The proposition should be written in English. The layout of the proposition should facilitate easy reading. Use the Verdana font at font size 8.5 (or similar).

REGISTRATION FORM (BASIC DATA)

1. Details of the applicant

1a. Lead Applicant (LA). The LA is the contact person for all correspondence.

Name, first name, title(s)	
Position	
Employment (fixed term/temporary)	
Institute	
Department	
Section	
Address	
Postcode	
City	
Telephone	
E-mail	

2a. Title of the project proposition and acronym

A short and specific title for the proposed research. The title entered here must be the same as the title submitted to the ISAAC submission system. Please also use a project acronym as part of the title.

2b. Keywords

(max. 6 keywords)

2c. Link with eScience Center expertise

Indicate the area(s) of expertise the proposed work is expected to require. In case your research does not exactly match one of the options, but you are of the opinion that your project idea still fits well within the aims and scope of the call, please direct your questions to open-calls@esciencecenter.nl.

- Software quality: developing workflow technologies, improving software practices, advancing software sustainability
- AI: machine learning, image processing
- Analytics: big data analytics, text analysis, visualization
- Data processing: databases, real-time data analysis, interoperability, and linked data
- Computing: exploitation of hardware accelerators, high performance computing, cloud computing, combining simulations

PROJECT PROPOSITION

3a. Summary of the project proposal (max. 150 words)

Please provide a non-expert summary of the proposal.

3b. Software and data accessibility and quality (Health Check)

The eScience Center expects a basic level of accessibility and quality for the data and software used in the projects. Applicants must therefore provide convincing arguments that the data (if any) and software serving as starting points of the research are usable, and do not require substantial cleaning or overhaul. For research software and data that are crucial to the research, the proposal must include the following information:

On data (if applicable):

- *A location where the data can be accessed (preferably a URL).*
- *The license under which the data is distributed (if any).*
- *Special conditions limiting the use of the data (e.g. AVG/GDPR).*

On software (always):

- *A location where the software can be accessed (preferably a URL to a version control system).*
- *The license under which the software is distributed (if any).*
- *A location where the documentation can be accessed (preferably a URL).*

If the data or software are not available online as open data or open source, details must be provided, such as clear metadata, such that an accessibility and quality check can be performed. Please contact the eScience Center to discuss alternatives.

Your institute may employ data stewards who can advise on these topics. Additionally, information on software and data quality can be found at:

- <https://www.openaire.eu/how-to-openly-license-research-data>
- <https://www.openaire.eu/how-to-make-your-data-fair>
- <https://choosealicense.com>
- <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00068>

ADMINISTRATIVE DETAILS

Proposal submission

The proposition should be submitted as a PDF file via the electronic application system ISAAC **before Thursday 16 March 2023, 14:00 CET**. More information on the use of ISAAC is available at www.nwo.nl. The proposal must be submitted from the ISAAC account of the Lead Applicant.

For technical questions about the use of ISAAC, please contact the ISAAC helpdesk. Applicants are requested to read the ISAAC manual before consulting the helpdesk. The ISAAC helpdesk is available from Monday to Friday from 10:00 to 17:00 hours on +31 (0)20 346 7179. You can also send your questions by email to isaac.helpdesk@nwo.nl. You will receive a reply within two working days.

More information

For more information, please check www.esciencecenter.nl or contact:

Program Officer NWO
Email: e-science@nwo.nl

Programme Management Netherlands eScience Center
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Email: open-calls@esciencecenter.nl